

APIMONDIA

International Federation of Beekeepers' Associations

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An Open letter

APIMONDIA STATEMENT ON HONEY ANTI-DUMPING CASE - USA

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Apimondia is the International Federation of Beekeepers' Associations. We represent beekeepers worldwide and promote scientific, ecological and economic apicultural development in all countries. Apimondia fosters international collaboration and the co-operation of beekeeper associations, scientific bodies and others involved in apiculture worldwide. We provide expert technical advice to organisations such as the United Nations through FAO, Interpol and policy makers in all continents.

Apimondia has learned that the US is being petitioned to impose anti-dumping measures against five countries: India, Vietnam, Ukraine, Brazil and Argentina (from the most important exporters to the US).

It is understandable that the American beekeepers' market must be protected as well as the market of other beekeepers in the world, however we cannot support this unilateral approach.

The main cause of the fall in prices on international markets comes from the sale of honeys that do not correspond to the criteria imposed on American beekeepers and the massive presence of fraud.

The anti-dumping measures do not correct this state of affairs but rather generate an increase in competition on other markets with a new drop in prices which will eventually have a very deleterious effect on the whole sector. One can also fear a reinforcement of honey fraud to maintain access to US markets.

Instead of imposing this international blockade, we recommend the reinforcement of existing anti-fraud efforts. It would be important to increase the use of new methods of fraud detection available today, which have clearly indicated that honey fraud is all too common. At the same time, it is essential to recognize that some commercial partners export quantities of honey that sometimes far exceed their real production capacities.

We are convinced that the implementation of new anti-dumping measures will have a very quick and negative effect on world honey prices. It can also have an impact on the intrinsic quality of honey, which is not possible with the implementation of anti-dumping measures.

Apimondia implores the US Department of Commerce and the International Trade Commission to understand that this case should not be seen as a “normal” dumping case. It has far reaching strategic implications for global food security and food sovereignty at a time when the world’s population and food supply systems are already seriously stretched and compromised by climate change and the global COVID-19 pandemic. COVID-19 has caused a resurgence of beekeeping as unemployed people leave urban areas to seek sources of income in rural areas.

Apimondia stands ready to provide independent experts (who are not involved as parties to this case from any of the countries involved) to assist the US Department of Commerce and the International Trade Commission to understand the technical and economic complexities and the surrounding issues, as you consider the case.

Apimondia can assist to provide technical information and to foster solutions. This case should rightly be seen as a very real cry for help by the US beekeeping sector, however collectively we must find other solutions. This is not just a US issue.

Apimondia has appointed the Dean of Apimondia, Mr. Gilles Ratia, as the first contact person in relation to this issue and the lead technical contact as Mr. Etienne Bruneau, President of the Apimondia Scientific Commission for Beekeeping Technology and Quality, neither of whom have any involvement in this case.

Their contact details are as follows:

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Your sincerely,

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Dean of Apimondia

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